

Śaiva Magic

By Aaron Ullrey, Independent

Entry tags: Religious Group, Indic Buddhist Traditions, Jain Traditions, Hinduism, Indic Religious Traditions

Magic in South Asia consists of pragmatic rituals aimed to transform the everyday world on behalf of a single practitioner or client; it originates and is most fully represented in the Śaiva tantras, even though Śaiva ritual techniques can be found in Buddhist and Jain tantras. Śaiva magic is constituted by the six magic ritual results (ṣaṭkarman), fantastic acts and enchanted items (indrajāla, kautukakarman), and conjuring (yakṣiṇisādhana). Though such rites are prefigured by techniques found in the Vedas, Epic, and Legal literature--especially those practices labeled sorcery (abhiçāra), root-work (mūlakarman), and medicine craft (auśadhi)--the full bloom of Śaiva magic is found in the tantras. Magic is not to be confused with the perfections (siddhis) displayed by thaumaturges (siddhas) or the yoga powers displayed by perfected strivers (yogīs); magic is the realm of the, often singular, ritual practitioner (sādhaka).

Date Range: 800 CE - 1500 CE

Region: South Asia (India, Sri Lanka, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Nepal)

Region tags: Asia, South Asia

Śaiva magic tantra texts are found in manuscript repositories throughout South Asia: India, Sri Lanka, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Nepal. Ritual techniques of magic are known throughout the popular cultures of South Asia.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Key Śaiva magic texts include the Uḍḍīśatantra, Uḍḍāmeśvaratantra, Ṣaṭkarmadīpikā, Ḍāmaratantra, Kāmaratna, Dāttatreyantra, to name a few.
- Source 2: Ullrey, Aaron Michael. Grim Grimoires: Pragmatic Rituals in the Magic Tantras. Dissertation, University of California Santa Barbara, 2016, UMI: 10249986
- Source 3: Goudriaan, Teun. Māyā Divine and Human. Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 1978.

Notes: Śaiva magic tantra are found in handwritten manuscripts, edited editions containing just the texts, and, most commonly, in edited editions with learned commentary by a pandit, usually the editor of the text. These later sources are commonly found throughout Indian book stores and have enjoyed wide publication in the twentieth century. In the twenty-first century english translations are beginning to be published.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: While the Śaiva are the most common and historically constant proponents of magic, both Buddhism and Jainism, especially in the medieval period (sixth to thirteenth century) borrowed from Śaiva magic and often expanded and nuanced it to fit their own categories. Magic in Islam contains currents from Persian and Sanskrit cultures, the Sanskrit current is thoroughly Śaiva.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: While generally Śaiva, the text describe no initiations and very few regulations for practitioners. Magic should be considered an additional practice on top of already established affiliation.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: When performed for a clients, as opposed to performed to benefit the performer, the clients would often be the wealthy and powerful. In the case of a purohita or courtly priest-sorcerer, the magician would necessarily have the support of a ruler.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative

and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Scriptures are written in Sanskrit and vernacular, though the Sanskrit sources are considered revelations from either Lord Śiva or Rāvaṇa, demon king of Lanka. Scriptures range from theoretical systematic sciences of magic, akin to culinary arts, to lists of spells, akin to cookbooks, to mere unorganized lists of mantra spalls.

↳ Are they oral:

– No

– Yes

Notes: Vernacular oral traditions of magic are described in ethnography, but such traditions do not stray far from Sanskrit discourse.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: Usually revealed by Śiva to a curious Goddess. The site of revelation is a glorious and heavenly mountain top.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Other than Śiva, the demon king of Lanka, i.e. Rāvaṇa, reveals magic tantras. He is considered a master of medicine and the arts, throughout South India his magic sources are considered equal to his works on medicine.

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Occasional human authors are mentioned in the texts, but their writing would be considered equivalent to the high god.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: While the texts are considered revealed, the hand of man is always acknowledged. Some texts argue that only the mantra spells are revealed and the rituals and magical techniques were later filled in by human authors.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: The iconography of deities invoked for magic results is often intricate and to be either visualized, incorporated into paintings used in the rituals, placed upon divine effigies in the rites, or to be mimicked by the practitioner.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Notes: The gods are not unique but are the ever present corpus of high and low gods encountered throughout Hindu polytheism.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: This distinction is found, but it is rarely addressed in notions of soteriology. Most of the beliefs in magic overlap with the sect to which the believer may belong or to general Hindu polytheism.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The presence of ghosts and spirits are constant. Practices of goddess conjuring often guarantee a positive rebirth in a kingly or wealthy family and sometimes describe rebirth in or transportation to a heaven realm.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - No
 - Notes: The high god Śiva is notoriously ambivalent. The revealer gods and goddesses are also ambivalent.
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– Yes

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– Yes

Notes: The world of Śaiva magic is thoroughly polytheistic. Śiva is thought to reign over many of the other deities, but the deities in magic are usually directly encountered without need of the high god as intermediary.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– No

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– No

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Human spirits are generally afflictive. They cause possession or weak general havoc on the lives of the living. The mechanics of these spirits depend on the sect of the practitioner or client. The magic tantras merely describe means for expelling such spirits.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: This depends upon the spirit. The spirit's in question are usually afflictive, causing possession or merely wreaking havoc in the mundane world.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Human spirits have a memory of life for a number of generations before they fade into the unified land of the faceless dead.
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: While spirits are generally invisible, spirits do reveal themselves as the result of conjuring. Should the conjuring be effective a goddess or demi goddess will reveal herself. In other cases a being will reveal itself to terrify or attack a practitioner's

enemies.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: The non-human beings usually have a particular domain or realm of life activity over which they specialize.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal

essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Wrangling supernatural beings is a main concern. Supernatural beings can bestow auspiciousness, blessings, and wealth, but they can also ruin a person in the world. Furthermore, supernatural beings may be sent to attack and destroy the enemies and rivals of the sorcerer.

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: The lowest of beings exhibit the type of hunger found in starving tigers. They must be fed to prevent supernatural attack.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group possess a pantheon of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are often associated into clans. For instance, yakṣinīs are all in different orders but their head man and father is thought to be Kubera, lord of the Yakṣas.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– No

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: These being intercede in sexual matters from enabling sexual desire to determining the sex and wellbeing of a child.

↳ Adultery:

– No

↳ Incest:

– No

↳ Other sexual practices:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Field doesn't know

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– No

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Sorcery is one of the main ways to manipulate these beings to keep them from harming the individual or to cast them against the individual's rivals.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– No

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– No

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings mete out all sorts of punishments for being in state of impurity, but they also afflict folk at seeming random, requiring the intercession of the sorcerer.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– No

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

– Yes

Notes: All sorts of misfortunes are considered the result of magic or as something requiring magical mediation.

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– No

Notes: Much of the work in Śaiva magic is to discern the cause or rewards and punishments and to encourage/discourage them.

– Yes

Notes: The essence of magic is inviting the deities to display good fortune, however the cause of the good fortune in magic is usually the perfect mechanical execution of the magical rite.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: Occasionally the rewards are positive or wealthy rebirths, but the majority of rewards are this worldly and effect the everyday world.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: All the rewards at hands can be secured through specific magic rites.

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - No
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

- No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The magic sources are devoid of ethics and morality. The only distinction is that what is effective and promotes the desires of the practitioner is good. Often, when describing rituals to make folk hate each other or kill a person, the reason for doing the rite is to take the victims wealth and family.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular

Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: The rituals performed by sorcerers involve manipulating substances that are dangerous. These substances are often impure but are also often poisonous to consume or are derived from dangerous animals, including poison, fangs, and claws.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Notes: There is a surprising lack of ethics. Contemporary vernacular discourse lays ethical prescriptions on magic, suggesting one should not kill other human beings or seduce another man's wife, but such arguments are absent from the root texts.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Small-scale religious practice is the hallmark of the Śaiva magic. Magic rituals are discrete and made effective by proper placation of an invisible entity or the perfect implementation of a ritual technique (including mantra, combination of ingredients, manipulating effigies, and so forth) rather

than personal charisma, accomplishment, or state of graceful connection to a deity.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This all depends on the individual practitioner and the type of practice.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: The social group of practitioners is not specified; they are subjects and members of whatever group corresponds to their normal life outside of practicing magic.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: A primary task of a sorcerer is to control floods and cause rains when needed. The water management is notably supernatural.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: While the main religious language is Sanskrit, the magic tantras use a type of nonstandard Sanskrit common for tantras. Furthermore, the magic sources use nonsense (or non-semantic) seed syllable to convey power and effectiveness to spells.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: Śaiva magic uses the traditional Indian and Śaiva calendar, but the spells are often timed to be performed during specific times of the year and astrological conjunctions according to be effective. For instance, killing rites are done during the hottest times of the summer and often at the hottest time of the day, whereas prosperity increase rites are done during the cool times of the year when the crops are growing and animals fattening.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know